

A Rapid Gravimetric Determination of Copper in Ores, Alloys and Complexes using 4-Amino-5-Mercapto-3-Methyl-4, 1, 2-Triazole and Characterization of the Copper Complex

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A simple, rapid and accurate gravimetric method has been developed for the determination of copper(II) with 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-4, 1, 2-triazole. Quantitative precipitation of copper occurs in ammoniacal medium. The reagent is specific for copper in ammoniacal tartarate medium. The complex $Cu(C_4H_5N_3S)$ can be weighed after drying at 120-130°. The determination can also be done in presence of a large number of cations. The method is successfully applied for ores, alloys and complexes of copper. The copper complex was characterized by (a) analytical data, (b) TGA and oxidation state studies and (c) i.r. spectra. The average relative error for the determination of copper in samples containing 10-60 mg. is 0.16%.

THERE is growing interest in the use of sulphur containing organic compounds in analytical as well as structural studies of metal complexes. This is due to the remarkable property of sulphur atom as a potential donor to form stable and well characterized complexes. A large number of organic thio compounds useful as analytical reagents are reported in literature¹⁻⁸. The present investigation reports the use of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-4, 1, 2-triazole as a reagent for copper.

In the course of our studies of metal complexes to elucidate their structures, it was observed that copper(II) in ammoniacal medium was quantitatively precipitated as a dark green complex on treatment with an aqueous solution of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-4, 1, 2-triazole and the precipitate rapidly changed to light grey. On analysis it was found that the precipitate is a 1 : 1 complex of copper with the ligand. This aroused our interest in investigating this quantitative precipitation.

The method is based on the fact that Cu(II) forms a light grey precipitate in ammoniacal tartarate medium in which most of the cations do not interfere and that the precipitation of copper is quantitative. Thus the reagent is specific for copper. The precipitate formed is insoluble in hot water unlike the reagent, so that the precipitate can be washed with hot water to remove the excess reagent. This method requires no critical pH control. The entire experiment can be completed in much less than two hours.

Fig. 1. The ligand 4-amino-3-methyl-5-mercapto-4,1,2-Triazole.

Materials: The chemicals used were all of AnalaR or chemically pure grade. The reagent was prepared by the method^{9,10} given in literature. It has the molecular formula $C_4H_5N_3S$ with probable structure as given in Figure 1.

The stock solution of copper(II) was prepared by dissolving in distilled water a known amount of A.R. $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ crystals and making up to known volume. The solution was standardised by iodimetric method¹¹. Aliquots of this solution were used for estimation. Air damp semi-micro balance and corning sintered glass crucible of porosity G-4 were used.

Solutions of various metal ions were prepared by dissolving the respective chlorides or sulphates in concentrations of 2-3mg/ml in water. In testing the interference by lead, lead nitrate and copper nitrate solutions were used. In the analyses of brass and bronze turnings obtained from alloy samples were used.

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Experimental

In a 250 ml. beaker, an aliquot of the stock solution was diluted to 100 ml. followed by addition of 1 : 1 ammonia solution till an intense blue colour developed. 2-3 ml. of 1 : 1 ammonia solution were added in excess. The solution was heated nearly to boiling. To the hot solution was added a slight excess of the hot reagent in the form of 1% aqueous solution with constant stirring until the blue colour of Cu^{2+} ions disappeared completely. A light grey precipitate becomes granular on being digested on a water bath for 15-20 minutes. The precipitate was filtered hot through a previously weighted sintered glass crucible and washed thoroughly with hot water. The precipitate was dried in an air-oven at 120-130° to constant weight and weighed as $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})$. The conversion factor from copper complex to copper is 0.33.

Effect of diverse ions: Various metal ions were added to study their effect on the quantitative estimation of copper.

To a solution containing 20.64 mg. of copper(II) were added solutions containing different foreign ions, 2-3 g. of tartaric acid and copper was estimated as described above.

It was found that there was no interference from most of the metals generally associated with copper in its ores and alloys.

Application of the method to copper ores, alloys and complexes:

The method described above is quite suited for the estimation of copper in ores, alloys and complexes of copper. The results obtained are reproducible besides being accurate, comparable with conventional gravimetric and iodimetric methods and yet got in much less time. Further the method works where many conventional gravimetric methods fail because of interference of foreign ions.

Procedure for copper ores, alloys and complexes of copper:

The copper ore was dissolved in aqua regia, heated to fuming with concentrated sulphuric acid, diluted, filtered and made up to a known volume. The alloys of copper were dissolved in 1 : 1 nitric acid, diluted, filtered to remove metastannic acid and the filtrate was made up to a known volume. An aliquot of the sample solutions containing 20-60 mg. of copper was used for estimation by the method described.

In the case of the triazole complexes of copper known amounts were decomposed repeatedly with aqua regia or concentrated nitric acid and evaporated nearly to dryness. The residue was

dissolved in water, diluted to about 100 ml. and copper estimated as described.

In the estimation of copper from copper quinaldinate complex, a known amount of the complex was dissolved in cold in minimum amount of concentrated nitric acid, 1 : 1 ammonia was added till a deep blue colour, the solution diluted and the metal estimated as described.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results of the reagent and the copper complex are given in table 1. The analyses

TABLE—1. ANALYTICAL RESULTS OF THE REAGENT AND THE COPPER COMPLEX

Compound		C	H	N	S	Cu
$\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S}$ (reagent)	Calcd.	27.70	4.62	43.1	24.62	-
	Found	27.81	3.54	42.8	24.45	-
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})$	Calcd.	18.70	2.60	29.08	16.62	33.00
	Found	18.70	2.67	28.75	17.16	32.92

of C, H and N of the reagent and the complex were done by the Micro Analytical Section of Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow and the estimation of sulphur and copper were done on semi-micro scale by standard methods¹¹. The sulphur was estimated by the alkali fusion method and copper by the acid dissolution method.

TABLE—2. DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN PRESENCE OF VARIOUS METAL IONS

Foreign ion	Copper present in solution *20.64 mg.		
	Qty. of foreign ion added	Copper found	Error
	mg.	mg.	%
As(III)	20.0	20.53	-0.53
	40.0	20.59	-0.24
Sb(III)	15.0	20.72	+0.39
	30.0	20.65	+0.05
Bi(III)	15.0	20.59	-0.24
	30.0	20.53	-0.53
Sn(II)	18.0	20.72	+0.39
	36.0	20.65	+0.05
Pb(II)	20.00	20.59	-0.24
	40.00	20.70	+0.29
Hg(II)	20.0	20.59	-0.24
	40.0	20.78	+0.68
Fe(III)	15.0	20.53	-0.53
	30.0	20.72	+0.39
Al(III)	22.0	20.59	-0.24
	40.0	20.65	+0.05
Mn(II)	20.0	20.65	+0.05
	40.0	20.59	-0.24
Ni(II)	20.0	20.72	-0.39
	40.0	20.62	-0.10
Co(II)	20.0	20.78	+0.68
	40.0	20.72	+0.39
Zn(II)	20.0	20.62	-0.10
	40.0	20.58	-0.29
Mg(II)	20.0	20.72	+0.39
	40.0	20.65	+0.05

*Found by copper quinaldinate method.

Results of gravimetric estimation of copper free from other metal ions with aliquots containing 10 to 60 mg. of copper are accurate with $\pm 0.16\%$. The results of copper estimation with the ligand in presence of other metal ions are given in Table 2. Similarly the results of estimations of copper to determine the precision of the method at 40 mg. level show a relative standard deviation of within $\pm 0.13\%$. The results of determination of copper from its ores, alloys and complexes are given in Table 3. From the results, it is clear that the following metal

TABLE—3. ESTIMATION OF COPPER IN ORES, ALLOYS AND COMPLEXES OF COPPER

Sample	% copper present	% copper found
1. Copper ore concentrate	*3.81	3.77
2. Enriched copper ore concentrate	*25.4	25.3
3. Bronze	*84.3	84.25
4. Brass	*62.6	62.40
5. $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	14.93	14.71
6. $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})$	33.00	32.92
7. $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S}_2)_2$	17.77	17.92

*Found by iodimetric method.

- 1) Obtained from Chitradurga Mines in Karnataka State and concentrated by the bacterial leaching process in the Metallurgy Department of the College.
- 2) Obtained after concentration of ores from Chitradurga.
- 5) Copper complex of quinaldonic acid.
- 6) Copper complex with 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-4, 1, 2-triazole.
- 7) Copper complex of 4-amino-3-5-dimercapto-4, 1, 2-triazole.

ions do not interfere: As(III), Sb(III), Bi(III), Sn(II), Pb(II), Hg(II), Fe(III), Al(III), Mn(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Mg(II). The only common metal ions which interfere are: Ti(I), Ag(I) and Cd(II) as they also form the respective complexes under similar conditions. However, copper can still be estimated when Ag(I) and Ti(I) are present by first separating these ions as their respective chlorides and then following the usual procedure. In the case of Cd(II) (which is seldom associated with copper in its ores and alloys) Cu can be complexed with KCN, Cd precipitated as CdS, separated and the Cu-Complex decomposed with concentrated nitric acid repeatedly and then estimated as described.

Characterization of the copper complex :

i) *Elemental Analyses* : The results of elemental analyses of the complex show that copper to ligand ratio is 1 : 1.

ii) *Oxidation State Studies* :

(a) *Magnetic Susceptibility Measurements* : These measurements were made in Karnataka University, Dharwar with the help of a Gouy balance using cobalt mercury thiocyanate as the standard. The copper complex was found to be

diamagnetic. This indicates that either copper is in +1 oxidation state or there is metal-metal interaction^{12, 13} if the oxidation state be +2.

(b) *EPR studies* : EPR spectrum of the powdered sample taken on varian E-4 X-Band EPR Spectrometer in Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Madras also confirmed the spin-paired behaviour of the complex.

(c) *Redox titrations* : In order to confirm the +1 oxidation state of copper in the complex, it was subjected to redox study using A. R. Ferric alum and A. R. potassium dichromate solutions under nitrogen atmosphere as per procedure given in literature¹⁴. It was found that the equivalent of iron reduced by 1 g. atom of copper in the complex was 1.007 as against the expected value of 1. All these results confirm the oxidation state of copper as +1.

iii) *Thermogravimetric analysis* : The complex was subjected to TGA on stanten HI-SM recording instrument to ascertain the temperature range over which the complex has thermal stability. The results obtained indicate that the complex does not undergo any change in weight upto 260°. This range is wide enough to cover any exigencies in drying.

iv) *Infrared spectra*. The ligand molecule can exist in the thiol or the thione form as shown in Figure 2. In the solid as well solution phase it exists as tautomers. In order to ascertain the

Fig. 2. Thiol and Thione forms of the ligand.

existence of tautomeric forms and to know the mode of linkage with copper, infra-red spectra of the ligand and the copper complex were studied. Major bands in the i.r. spectra are given in Table 4. Systematic shifts in the position of the bands which can be assigned without much ambiguity gave clues to the mode of linkage.

i) The ligand molecule basically consists of HNCS or NCSH group apart from a methyl group and an amino group. Hence, one should expect thioamide bands^{12, 15, 16} in the spectrum of the ligand and those bands should shift in the spectrum of the copper complex. Whereas a band near 2500 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{S-H})$ indicates the thiol form of the ligand, the splitting of the band due to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ around 3000-3200 cm^{-1} because of interaction between the NH and NH_2 groups, indicates the thione form of the ligand.

TABLE-4. ASSIGNMENT OF THE MAJOR INFRARED BANDS (IN CM^{-1}) OF THE LIGAND AND THE COPPER COMPLEX

Ligand	Copper complex	Assignment
3260-3040 S b (split 4 bands)	3210 S s, 3100 S s	ν (N-H)
2930 m	2850 m	ν (C-H)
2510 m	-	ν (S-H)
1632 S s	1630 w sh	δ (N-H)
1580 S s	1610 S s	Thioamide I ^a
1380 S s, 1390 S s	1390 S s	(C-CH ₃)
1323 S s	1370-1280 S (split)	Thioamide II ^b
1044 m s	1017 m s	Thioamide III ^c
993 m s	972 m s	Thioamide IV ^d
750 S s	744 S s	τ (N-H)
-	408 w sh	ν (N-M) weak interaction
-	395 m s	ν (M-S)

^a due to δ (N-H) major contribution + ν (C=N) minor contribution

^b due to δ (N-H) minor contribution + ν (C=N) major contribution

^c due to ν (C-N) major contribution + ν (C=S) minor contribution

^d due to ν (C=S)

S=Strong, m=medium, w=weak, b=broad, s=sharp and sh=shoulder.

ii) This splitting is reduced in the spectrum of the complex due to deprotonation of the N-H group. Such deprotonation is in conformity with charge balance. The question now is whether the metal is bonded through nitrogen or sulphur of the ligand molecule. Cu(I) is a b-class metal¹⁷ and hence prefers to bond with highly polarizable S and not with hard base N. A further evidence to bonding through S comes from the disappearance of the band due to ν (S-H) and appearance of a band due to ν (M-S) in the spectrum of the complex.

iii) The band around 1600 cm^{-1} is assigned to thioamide band I which contains a major contribution from δ (N-H) and a minor contribution from ν (C=N). This band shifts slightly towards higher wave number side in the spectrum of the complex. But the band around 1320 cm^{-1} assigned to thioamide band II which has a major contribution from ν (C=N) shifts considerably to higher wave number side because bonding of Cu(I) through S localizes the double bond between carbon and nitrogen - unlike in the ligand as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Bonding scheme for complexation.

Thioamide band III around 1040 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand is due to major contribution from ν (C-N) and minor contribution from ν (C=S). Since in the spectrum of the complex the (C=S)

changes to (C-S) thioamide band III slightly shifts towards lower wave number side.

The thioamide band IV around 995 cm^{-1} is mostly due to ν (C=S). Since partial double bond character due to delocalization of charge in the ligand is lost in the complex, one should expect this band to shift considerably towards lower wave number side which is actually observed.

From this discussion it is clear that in the complex of Cu(I) with the ligand the metal is coordinated through sulphur. Like in most Cu(I) complexes this too must be a linear molecule with copper strongly bonded to S of one ligand molecule and weakly to N of another ligand molecule as

Fig. 4. Structure of Copper Complex.

shown in the Figure 4. However, ionic structure involving bonding through thiocarbonyl S cannot be ruled out.

Conclusion

- Oxidation state of copper in the complex is +1.
- The complex is stable over the temperature range of $100-260^\circ$.

iii) Accurate determination of copper is possible in presence of several associated metal ions.

iv) The reagent can be easily prepared and is less expensive.

v) Complete reduction of Cu(II) to Cu(I) is achieved in less than ten minutes unlike in the case of thiocyanate method with reduction by sulphur dioxide.

vi) Comparison of results given in Table 3 shows that the reagent can be used for gravimetric determination of copper, though at a poorer gravimetric factor compared to those methods using quinaldinic acid or 4-amino-3-5-dimercapto-4, 1, 2-triazole.

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